

MANAGEMENT CULTURE OF EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION LEADERSHIP. FORMATION OF CREATIVITY AND PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE IN PEDAGOGICAL MANAGEMENT

Sotvoldiyeva M.

Kokan University, Management of educational institutions, master's degree 1

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11368573>

Abstract. *In this article, there are suggestions and comments on the management culture of leading an educational institution and formation of creativity and professional competence in pedagogical management.*

Keywords: *"leadership style", education, institution, management, culture, management, creativity, competence, axiological approach, acmeological approach, creative approach, reflexive approach, manager, leader, social, economic, style, creativity.*

INTRODUCTION

One of the most urgent problems in modern science is the relationship between the concepts of "leader", "leader" or "leadership style" and "leadership style". Among them, the most important B.D. According to Pargin, the leader coordinates interpersonal relations in a certain group, is an element of the microenvironment, appears unexpectedly, and his position is less stable, his movement depends on the mood of the group, and he is more related to the activity of the group. makes decisions. And the leader coordinates official relations in groups considered as a social organization and is an element of the macro environment. The leader's position is more stable, and he has several times more powers, decision-making, commanding, assignment, and demanding rights in a given system. The decision-making process is somewhat more complex and involves many, many different situations, and these situations do not apply to just one group. When the leader operates in a small group of a certain broader social system, his scope of action is considered wide. According to some experts, leadership complements the concept of leadership in improving team performance. Researcher A. Nosirov expressed his opinion by emphasizing the importance of competence in leadership management.

1. Standard competence is the ability to define innovative tasks related to this activity;
2. The main competence is the ability to set innovative tasks related to this activity;
3. Sufficient competence, the ability to create new types of professional activity;
4. It is stated that professional competence is having knowledge of pedagogy and psychology, working on oneself consists in forming motivation in students [7, 2].

Researcher Temurov D - recommends the following principles for applying the knowledge of the management of the educational institution to practical activities:

1. Unity of consciousness and activity. This principle is the mastery of the knowledge of the management of the educational institution and its application in practical activities.
2. Scientific and ideological nature of educational institution management. This principle is guided by high idealism and scientifically based management.
3. Consistency and unity of management in educational institutions. This principle means that the effectiveness of leaders is gained in the democratic movement.

4. The leadership in the educational institution has humanitarian characteristics. This principle represents public interests and personal interests on the basis of social activity.

5. A comprehensive (complex) systematic approach to the management of educational institutions. This principle unites the employees of the educational institution in one social activity.

6. Orientation of the management of educational institutions to a specific goal. This principle is explained by the organization of actions based on the directions of activity of the educational institution in the social movement [8, 95-96].

So, today the word "management" has been modernized and enriched with the word "management". Today, our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev's attention to school education and his naming of 2023 as "the year of human dignity and quality education" gave a great inspiration to teachers and pedagogical leaders of all general education schools and to work selflessly in order to improve the quality of education. invited.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

"School leaders working in accordance with the rules of management, feeling the reforms in the field of education today, organize the management based on the rules of modern competence, strong instructional leadership, clearly defined goals, creative results expected from teachers, to study and teach. necessary environment, constant observation of students and class, strengthen family, school, neighborhood cooperative relations. New scientific research requires the organization of leadership work based on the initiative of a prosperous neighborhood, a prosperous neighborhood, a prosperous home, and a model family. "Management culture is a qualitative synthesis of administrative social and psychological processes of the leader in the successful implementation of professional and workmanship.

Every person who has the title "Leader" should always be an example to others with his appearance, cultural dress, demandingness, knowledge, and organization. Based on the above-mentioned considerations, we have analyzed the following cases about some shortcomings in the direction of the competence of the leader who is working in the field of preschool and school education today:

- lack of demand for management work in schools;
- lack of self-sacrifice, creativity, organization, creativity;
- low legal culture and literacy;
- lack of fairness, honesty and integrity;
- priority of locality and patriotism in the work process;
- Ignoring methodical associations, lack of initiative and entrepreneurship;
- incorrect distribution of team work in schools and low control;
- lack of professional and scientific experience [3, 83].

After reading the above comments, every talented person who wants to manage today's educational process based on the decisions they make in the field of education should organize their management work based on their professional competence. In general, success in educational institutions can be interpreted as the interest of the leader's relationship with the executive team. It depends significantly on ability.

An important management goal of a modern manager is to raise his employees to a moral and high level, to make them a morally healthy team. In general, the success of an educational institution depends on the ability of the leader to communicate how interested he is in the relationship with the performers.

According to G. Kuntz and S. O. Dannel, "if the subordinates are guided by the rules and needs of the leaders, they can work at about 60 or 65% of their potential, that is, to remain in their work. In order to simply perform their duties satisfactorily, in order to fully use the capabilities of subordinates, it is necessary for leaders to form appropriate judgments in them by implementing leadership. Leadership is a component of management aimed at influencing people and coordinating their activities. The elected or appointed leader performs a number of functions: determines and formulates the goals of the team's activity, plans this activity, determines the means and methods of stimulation, and carries out its control.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, in his teleconference with the staff of the public education system on August 23, 2019, expressed the following opinions: "One of the main tasks of a modern teacher is high professional competence and intellectual potential, loyalty, is his religious faith and his love for his profession. These qualities distinguish pedagogues from other professions."

In order to create creativity in today's students, today's pedagogue must have exemplary intelligence, have a perfect knowledge of modern educational laws, and have the ability to be creative in his profession.

Today's professor-teacher will have to teach his students to develop logical thinking and creativity, as well as forming human qualities such as loyalty to the Motherland, kindness, responsibility, tolerance, legal advice, innovative thinking, hard work. Formation of creative activities for future pedagogues will be as follows.

Creativity includes the following activities:

- Axeological approach;
- Acmeological approach;
- Creative approach;
- A reflexive approach.

The teacher's competence can be explained as follows:

- Purpose and content of the teacher's activity;
- Personal and professional qualities;
- Pedagogical skills, methods and technologies;
- Professional motivation.

In the course of the teacher's work, in the implementation of educational tasks, competence that is important throughout life is necessary. They include the following:

- Communicative competence;
- Innovative competence;
- Ability to solve problems;
- Creating a self-developing environment.

Communicative competence requires full communication skills from the teacher. Requires a positive relationship with students and team members in any situation. Information competence - the teacher must be aware of his subject and all the news related to it. Therefore, a pedagogue should have the skills to use information and computer technologies.

Theoretical materials are given to students on the subject of "Pedagogical tact and pedagogical ethics", and methodological advice is given for conducting seminar classes. Students should regularly work on themselves and reach the level of being able to complete the tasks of the given seminar using various information media and apply them in practical activities, that is, pedagogical competencies should be formed.

In the coverage of the topic "Culture and psychology of behavior in the work of a teacher, as well as pedagogical tact and pedagogical ethics", specific types of culture of behavior in the work of a teacher, the priority of universal values in the organization of communication, the characteristics and functions of pedagogical communication, the essence of pedagogical ethics and features, as well as knowledge of teacher's ethics and pedagogic tact. This knowledge is strengthened during practical and seminar classes. At the end of the subject, the student's knowledge is checked through tests or other assignments. The topics of each module are delivered to students in this way, they form knowledge and skills in this subject, develop the qualities of future teachers, and develop their pedagogical competence [5].

In this regard, today the following requirements are imposed on participants in pedagogical management, i.e. teachers:

- in-depth knowledge of his subject and sufficient mastery of its methodology;
- to have a broad scientific outlook and deep faith;
- deep understanding of social need and moral necessity;
- deep understanding of social and civic duty;
- to be socially and politically active;
- he loves his profession and children;
- to be mentally pedagogically intelligent and strive for innovation;
- deeply study the history, national values and traditions of their people and promote them;
- possess qualities such as pedagogical observation, organization, demandingness, determination, restraint, truthfulness, self-control;
- he should be fully capable of his profession and possess pedagogical tact (decency) [5].

CONCLUSION

In short, every pedagogue working in the educational system should direct all his knowledge and experience to improve the educational system.

REFERENCES

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people. - Tashkent: "Uzbekistan", 2017. - 488 p.
2. Kenjaboyev A, Kenjaboyeva D. Pedagogical deontology and competence. Termiz 2022. 100 pages.
3. Kenjaboyev A.E. Professional competence and pedagogical skills of the pedagogical leader. Modern education. 2020 No. 10. 83 pages.
4. Kenjaboyev A.E. "Professional competence and creativity of a modern teacher is a requirement of today." Journal of Public Education, 2020 No. 5.9-11 p.
5. M. Ochilov. "Teacher is the architect of the heart" Tashkent "Teacher" 2001.
6. Musurmanova O. "Pedagogical technologies - a factor of educational efficiency". T.: Youth publishing house. 2020, 56 pages.
7. Nosirov A. Journal of professional competence of the leader and management culture and education management. 2013 No. 6, 2 pages.
8. Temirov D. The integrity of pedagogical principles in the management of educational institutions. Educational management journal 2013 year No. 6. Pages 95-96.